

Śluzowce Czarnohory w Karpatach Wschodnich. — Mycetoza from the Czarnohora Mountains in the Polish Eastern Carpathians.

Mémoire

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Our knowledge of the Mycetoza of the Polish Carpathians is extremely scanty, and is on the whole of a fragmentary nature. These organisms are described in the not very numerous papers of various older authors (M. Raciński, J. Krupa, R. Gutwiński, B. Namysłowski), and deal chiefly with the Tatra and the Western Beskidy, as well as with the Rieszczady Mountains, whilst over the vast range of the Gorgany and Czarnohora Mountains in the Eastern Carpathians they have never been thoroughly studied.

Thanks to the kind invitation of Dr. T. Wilczyński, at the time Director of the High Mountain Botanical-Agricultural Station of Czarnohora, the author of this paper was enabled to devote two successive vacations (1924 and 1925) to the investigation of the Mycetoza of the unsearched Czarnohora Range. The terrain covered included the northeastern slopes of Czarnohora, i. e., the wooded area above the upper Pruth and its sources, enclosed on the north and west by the following summits: Kukul (1542 m.), Koźmieska (1575 m.), Howerla (2058 m.), Breskul (1910 m), Pożyżewska (1822 m), Dancerz (1818 m), Turkul (1935 m) and, Gutin Tomnatik (2018 m), and on the south and east extending as far as Szpyci (1886 m) and Wielka and Mała Mariszewska (1514 and 1451 m). In a vertical direction this terrain was enclosed within the 1000–1600 m isohyps. The extensive spruce fo-

rests (*Piceetum excelsae*) covering the slopes of the mountains were in places in a completely wild and virgin condition. Many of them had suffered during the World war from the obstinately contested battles fought in this region, as a result of which certain of the Czarnohora forests were after the war attacked by the bark-beetles. The numerous decaying and rotting tree-stumps, together with the abundant rain- and snow-falls characteristic of these mountains constituted good conditions for the development of numerous Mycetoza in these forests. The extensive subalpine areas above the upper forest limit (1450–1625 m), covered by dense growths of dwarf mountain pine (*Pinus mughus*) and of dwarf mountain alder (*Alnus viridis*), with an admixture of mountain juniper (*Juniperus nana*) and of Carpathian rhododendron (*Rhododendron Kotschyi*) do not afford suitable conditions for the development of Mycetoza, and the alpine zone (1950–2058 m) of the »połoniny« (mountain meadows or pastures) is similarly free of these organisms in the Czarnohora Range.

The two consecutive seasons during which the author prosecuted his investigations constitute too short a period of time to allow the exploration of the Czarnohora Range material to be considered to be concluded. In comparison with the extraordinary variety of forms found by the eminent Roumanian scientist Marcel Brândza in the neighbouring Moldavian Carpathians¹⁾, the Mycetoza found in the Czarnohora Mts. are represented far less numerously, both as regards the numbers of species and the frequency of their occurrence. During the years 1924 and 1925 a total of 69 species was found in the Czarnohora forests; this number, while undoubtedly less than the number actually present, allows of the drawing of certain general conclusions.

The comparatively small number of species found is connected with the extreme uniformity of the substratum, consisting almost exclusively of decaying spruce wood (*Picea excelsa*)²⁾. The virtually complete absence of deciduous trees in the higher moun-

¹⁾ During the twelve years of Dr Brândza's investigations 181 species of Mycetoza have been discovered, chiefly in a small area of mixed mountain forests in the neighbourhood of Monastirea Neamtu, district Neamtu, Moldavia.

²⁾ The fir-tree (*Abies alba*) occurs only in lower forest belt of the Czarnohora.

tain forest belt a priori excludes the possibility of the occurrence of a whole range of Mycetozoa, only beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) playing a certain rôle as a substratum in the lower placed portions of the Czarnohora forests. Scrub, consisting of *Pinus mughus* and *Alnus viridis*, does not provide, as has already been mentioned, favourable conditions for the development of Mycetozoa¹⁾.

No alpine forms of the type of «*espèces nivales*» of Ch. Meylan have been encountered in Czarnohora, in spite of a careful search among dead herbage on the borders of forests and on alpine pastures. Even in the vicinity of thawing patches of snow lying in the neighbourhood of decaying vegetable débris the author was unable to discover any Mycetozoa. It is possible that these should have been searched for in the early spring or before the commencement of winter, or that certain local factors come into play here, rendering conditions very different to those of the Swiss Alps or Jura Mountains.

The Mycetozoa found by the author in this part of the Carpathians are distinguished by the strikingly small number, both qualitatively and quantitatively, of representatives of the *Calcarina* »group«. This circumstance may be ascribed not only to the uniformity of the substratum, but also undoubtedly to the low calcium content of the Flysh strata forming the Czarnohora Range, and consisting chiefly of Oligocene Magura sandstones. In certain pasture and forest areas excessive acidity of the soil also undoubtedly exerts a certain effect.

The complete absence or sporadic occurrence of many Mycetozoa, common in lowland terrains, is also a striking feature of the Czarnohora region. This may, apart from the above stated reasons, be due to unfavourable local climatic and atmospheric conditions, such as too low temperature of the summer months, etc.²⁾

¹⁾ I was not able to examine the small timber-line pine (*Pinus Cembra*) groves of the Gadżyna valley.

²⁾ The possibility that some Mycetozoa, in particular very minute forms (e. g. *Echinostelium minutum* De Bary), may have been overlooked in certain terrains should also be borne in mind: this may occur to even the most practised collectors. On the other hand, the discovery in a given locality of species not found by our predecessors should not always be ascribed to their lack of skill in research, as, at the time when the examination of the terrain was made these species may, as a result of unfavourable conditions, have been entirely absent.

On the 69 species found on Czarnohora 14 have been for the first time discovered on the territory of the Polish Republic. These are:

- Barbeyella minutissima* Meylan.
Clastoderma debaryanum Blytt.
Colloderma oculatum (Lippert).
Cribraria dictydioides Cooke et Balf.
Cribraria ferruginea Meylan.
Cribraria rubiginosa Fries.
Diachea cerifera G. Lister.
Dianema corticatum Lister.
Diderma floriforme Pers.
Diderma montanum Meylan.
Lamproderma echinulatum (Berkeley).
Margarita metallica (Berk. et Br.)
Stemonitis hyperopta Meylan.
Stemonitis pallida Wingate.

Apart from these the discovery on Czarnohora of the exceedingly rare *Kleistobolus pusillus* Lippert is noteworthy. This form was hitherto encountered only in one spot, in the Polish Tatra Mtns., where it was discovered in 1926 by the present author.

The systematic classification applied in this paper is based on the system of E. Jahn¹⁾, which is less artificial than that adopted in the Monographies of A. and G. Lister, T. H. Macbride and H. Schinz.

The author has sincere pleasure in expression his gratitude to Dr. Tadeusz Wilczyński for his hospitality and kindness in granting me the use of the laboratory of the High Mountain Botanical-Agricultural Station of Czarnohora. The author wishes also to thank his brother, Mr. Bohdan Jarocki for his assistance during 1925.

Specimens of the Czarnohoran Mycetoza have been deposited in the collections of the Physiographic Museum of the Polish Academy of Sciences at Cracow.

¹⁾ E. Jahn. Myxomycetenstudien. 12. Das System der Myxomyceten. Berichte der Deutsch. Bot. Ges. Jahrg. 1928, Bd. XLVI, 1928.

E. Jahn. Myxomycetes in: A. Engler und K. Prantl, Die natürlichen Pflanzenfamilien. 2 Band, 2 Aufl. Leipzig 1928.

Annotated list of species recorded from Czarnohora.

Ceratiomyxidae.

Ceratiomyxa Schroeter.

1. *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* (Macbride). Not unfrequent¹⁾ on moist decaying trunks of coniferous and deciduous trees, especially during the early part of summer.

Var. *porioides* (Alb. et Schw.). Comparatively not common in forests of this country.

Reticulariidae.

Reticularia Bulliard.

2. *Reticularia lycoperdon* Bull. Two small aethalia²⁾ were found on a rotten beech stump (*Fagus sylvatica*) at Bystrzec, 27—VIII—1925.

Tubiferidae.

Tubifera Gmelin.

3. *Tubifera ferruginosa* Gmel. Very frequent in the Czarnohora Mts. on rotten wood of coniferous and deciduous trees.

The aethalia of this species are frequently infested by the larvae of *Epiclypta punctum* Stann. and *E. testacea* Edw. (*Di-*

¹⁾ Dr. F. X. Skupieński considers that this species is «relativement rare pour le territoire polonais» (Contribution à l'étude des Myxomycètes en Pologne: Bull. de la Soc. Mycol. de France, Tome XLII, 1926: loc. cit. p. 149). This statement is not accurate, since *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* belongs to the most common and widely distributed of our Mycetozoa.

²⁾ The preservation of the aethalia of Mycetozoa involves, as is well known, considerable difficulties, in view of their fragility and brittleness. I have for some time employed a simple method for the preservation of specimens for collections. After the thorough drying and disinfection of the specimen a 1—2% solution of celloidine in a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether (diluted collodium may also be used) is sprayed with the aid of an atomiser on the surface of the aethalium. After the film has dried, the operation is repeated several times, paying special attention to all fissures, depressions etc., and to the points of contact of the aethalium with the substratum. The aethalia of *Fuligo*, *Amaurochaete*, *Lindbladia*, *Tubifera* etc., treated in this way are very well adapted to preservation in collections. The imperceptible film of colourless celloidine protects the aethalium from damage, prevents the spilling of spores, and protects from insects.

ptera, *Fungivoridae*). On the other hand, these larvae are often infested by the parasitic larvae of the hymenopter *Aperileptus obliquus* Thom. (*Ichneumonidae*)¹.

Lycogalidae.

Lycogala Adanson.

4. *Lycogala epidendrum* (Fries). Common throughout the summer and autumn months in all woods of Czarnohora.

Licciidae.

Licea Schrader.

5. *Licea flexuosa* (Pers.). Very common in the coniferous forests of Czarnohora, especially in wood-fellings on the weathered surface of old *Picea* stumps, which are sometimes almost dry and fully exposed to sunlight.

6. *L. minima* (Fries). Collected repeatedly from many places, occurring usually in scattered colonies. Probably not rare. The favourite habitat is the moist surface of very rotten logs of *Picea excelsa*. September. It appears to be the first Polish record of this *Licea*.

7. *L. pusilla* Schrader. Rare. Found on several occasions on decaying *Picea* logs. August.

This species was discovered for the first time in Poland by the late Professor J. Rostafiński who collected it at Stawczana Góra near Kielce.

Kleistobolus Lippert.

8. *Kleistobolus pusillus* Lippert. In examining specimens of wood collected from various localities in Czarnohora I found on a few of them small colonies of this interesting mycetozoon. In a few cases *Kleistobolus* was found on dead spruce wood covered with algae, together with *Colloderma oculatum* (Lippert) and *Barbeyella minutissima* Meylan. I also found

¹ For closer details see: J. Kinel and J. Noskiewicz, Zur Kenntnis der beiden paläarktischen *Epicyptha*-Arten (*Dipt.*, *Fungivoridae*). — Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne (Bulletin Entomologique de la Pologne), Vol. X, pag. 69–73; Lwów, 1931.

this form on a decayed beech log associated with *Lamproderma arcyrionema* Rostaf.

The exceedingly minute dimensions of the sporangia make it extremely difficult to observe this form during field operations. The Czarnohora specimens in no way differ from those of the Tatra Mts., discovered and fully described by me in 1926¹⁾, as well as, on the basis of my material, by Miss G. Lister in 1927²⁾.

Cribrariidae.

Lindbladia Fries.

9. *Lindbladia effusa* (Ehrenberg). Frequent on rotten coniferous wood and on decaying vegetable debris. In August 1925 numerous very large aethalia (20—35 cm in diam.) were collected at Mt. Pożyżewska and Mt. Dancerz on rotting *Picea* stumps in full sunshine.

The immature stage of aethalium of this species is of a pale cream colour.

Cribraria Persoon.

10. *Cribraria argillacea* Pers. This is one of commonest species of this genus in forests of Czarnohora.

11. *C. rubiginosa* Fries. Rare. Was found only once at Mt. Mała Mariszewska on wood-fibres of decaying *Picea excelsa*.

No Polish record of this *Cribraria* has been previously published.

12. *C. ferruginea* Meylan. This species, originally described in 1913 from Switzerland, occurs rarely in the Czarnohora Range. I collected it at Mt. Homul, Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Mała Mariszewska, at an altitude from 1200 to 1300 m, on very rotten trunks of *Picea excelsa*. Our specimens correspond in all respects

¹⁾ J. Jaroeki. On the morphology and systematical value of the mycetozoon *Kleistobolus pusillus* Lippert. Bull. International de l'Académie Polonaise des Sciences et des Lettres. Série B. N° 9—10 (Novembre-Décembre) 1926; pag. 849—858. planche 20.

²⁾ G. Lister. *Kleistobolus* Lippert, a genus of Mycetozoa revived. The Journal of Botany, July 1927; pag. 202—203. See also: E. Jahn. Myxomycetes in: A. Engler und K. Prantl, Die natürlichen Pflanzenfamilien. 2 Bd., 2 Aufl., 1928; pag. 319.

with the description of Ch. Meylan. The plasmodium was not observed. This is the first Polish record of this species.

13. *C. vulgaris* Schrader. Occurs on decayed coniferous wood during the summer months. Collected at Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz, Mt. Homul and Mt. Koźmieska.

14. *C. splendens* Schrad. Found several times in July on rotting logs of spruce at Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Homul.

15. *C. intricata* Schrad. Collected on several occasions from rotting spruce logs.

16. *C. dictydioides* Cooke et Balfour. Frequent during the summer months on rotting spruce logs.

17. *C. tenella* Schrader. Found several times on very rotting spruce logs. Collections were made at Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Homul and Mt. Koźmieska.

18. *C. piriformis* Schrad. On rotting spruce stumps. Collected at Mt. Homul.

19. *C. microcarpa* Pers. Found once at Mt. Koźmieska on a rotting spruce stump.

20. *C. purpurea* Schrad. Found several times in September 1925 on very rotten logs of *Picea excelsa*, at Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Homul and at Zaroślak.

Dictydium Schrader.

21. *Dictydium cancellatum* (Batsch). Common on rotten *Picea* wood at various points of this region. On one occasion it was found at Mt. Dancerz on a rotting stump of *Pinus mughus*.

Stemonitidae.

Stemonitis Gleditsch.

22. *Stemonitis fusca* (Roth). Frequent on rotten wood of spruce, especially in drier situations.

Var. *confluens* Lister. Found twice at Mt. Mała Mariszewska on old beech logs. September 1925.

23. *S. hyperopta* Meylan. Not uncommon on decaying mossy trunks of *Picea excelsa*. VI—VII.

This is the first Polish record of this species.

24. *S. pallida* Wingate. Collected on several occasions from mossy *Picea* logs. July.

It has not been recorded hitherto from Poland. Dr. M. Brândza reports its frequent occurrence in the mountains of Moldavia.

25. *S. flavogenita* Jahn. Not unfrequent on mossy logs of *Picea excelsa*. July.

26. *S. ferruginea* Ehrenb. Common everywhere on rotting coniferous trunks. VI—IX.

Comatricha Preuss.

27. *Comatricha nigra* Schroeter. Fairly common and widely distributed over the wooded slopes of Czarnohora. Occurs usually in large colonies, principally on the under surface of the old trunks of *Picea excelsa*.

28. *C. lara* Rostaf. Found on several occasions on dead spruce wood.

29. *C. elegans* (Raciborski). Some specimens were discovered on a piece of rotten *Picea* wood amongst numerous sporangia of *Comatricha nigra*.

30. *C. typhoides* (Bull.). Frequent on rotting coniferous trunks. VI—VII. Specimens were collected from Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz, Mt. Koźmieska, Mt. Mała Mariszewska and Mt. Homul.

31. *C. pulchella* Rostaf. This species seems to be rare in Czarnohora. On dead *Picea* wood at Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Homul. July.

Enerthenema Bowman.

32. *Enerthenema papillatum* (Pers.). On fallen decorticated logs of *Picea excelsa*. Not common. Collected at Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Homul. VIII—IX.

Lamprodermatidae.

Lamproderma Rostafiński.

23. *Lamproderma echinulatum* (Berk.). Found only once in small quantity on a rotten trunk of *Fagus silvatica* at Mt. Mała Mariszewska (at an altitude 1100 m) in August 1924¹⁾. It is the first record of this rare species from Poland.

¹⁾ I am very much indebted to Miss G. Lister of the British Museum for the comparative specimens of this species from Aberdeen, Scotland.

34. *L. arcyriionema* Rostafiński. Rare. Found twice on rotting logs of *Fagus sylvatica* at Mt. Mała Mariszewska and at Bystrzec.

35. *L. columbinum* Pers. This variable species is very common in all localities of Czarnohora on fallen mossy logs of *Picea excelsa*.

36. *L. violaceum* (Fries) var.? Collected on mossy logs of *Picea excelsa* at Mt. Pożyżewska.

Echinosteliidae.

Clastoderma Blytt.

37. *Clastoderma debaryanum* Blytt. Found three times only but in profusion on fallen logs of *Picea excelsa* in a very advanced stage of decay. Collected at Mt. Koźmieska (3—IX—1925), Mt. Pożyżewska (6—IX—1925) and Zaroślak (12—IX—1925). Probably more widely distributed in suitable habitats.

According to my observations, the plasmodium of this species is dirty-white, watery-white, or colourless. In beginning the production of sporangia the plasmodium assumes the shape of hemispherical or lens-shaped drops scattered over the substratum. In its very early stages of development the sporangia are watery-white, whilst the stalk retains the darker colour of the plasmodium. The older sporangia gradually assume a pale rose-red colour, which similarly gradually darkens to brown.

Barbeyella Meylan.

38. *Barbeyella minutissima* Meylan. This interesting mycetozone is widely distributed in all spruce forests of the Czarnohora Range, at an elevation from 1100 to 1400 m. It occurs usually in damp situations, principally on the under moist surface of decaying logs of *Picea excelsa*, covered with wet mosses, liverworts and algae. I found it often associated with *Lamproderma columbinum*, *Colloderma oculatum*, *Lepidoderma tigrinum*, *Diderma radiatum* and *Trichia decipiens*. Collected repeatedly from many localities (Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz, Mt. Homul, Mtns. Wielka and Mała Mariszewska, Mt. Kukul, Mt. Koźmieska, Zaroślak etc.) in August and September 1924—1925.

This is the first record of this species for Poland and for the Carpathians. Outside Poland it has been recorded from Switzerland only. The structural characters of this minute form are very constant, and the Czarnohoran specimens of *Barbeyella* agree in all respects with Dr. Meylan's ¹⁾ topotypes from Suchet in the Swiss Jura Mountains ²⁾.

The colourless, hyaline plasmodium of *Barbeyella* is scattered over the substratum in the form of small drops. Very young sporangia initially possess the same character as plasmodium, but soon become opaque. Older sporangia are at first whitish, and later assume a light brown colour, which darkens progressively, until it is ultimately dark brown, almost black. In the completely developed state they are brownish-black or violet-black, and possess a matt or slightly glistening surface.

The sporangia possess a spherical or slightly elongated shape and measure 0.1 to 0.2 mm in diam. The base of the sporangium is slightly flattened, with the usual concavity to the interior of the sporangium in the vicinity of the columella. The length of the black, subulate stalk is 0.2 to 0.6 mm. The surface of the peridium is more or less granular, according to the number of granulations produced by the plasmodium. The fragments and lobes of peridium are somewhat concave, as a result of which the contours of the surface are angular, and resemble the sporangia of *Diderma rugosum* (Rex).

The places where the future peridial lobes and fragments develop are visible already in very young, still white sporangia, as marks on their external surface, and in these places refuse substances gradually accumulate. Older, light-brown sporangia possess a completely developed external structure of the peridium, in which the brownish fragments are separated from each other by well defined lighter streaks, which correspond to the later lines of dehiscence. The peridium of mature sporangia is distinctly segmented into a smaller or larger number of segments and lobes, which are polyangular in the upper, and irregularly

¹⁾ I am much indebted to Dr. Ch. Meylan (Ste Croix) for supplying me with those specimens.

²⁾ *Barbeyella minutissima* is not an exclusively alpine or mountain form. I found it also in 1926 in the lowland woods of the primeval Białowieża forest (Puszcza Białowieska).

petal-shaped in the lower portions of the sporangium. The peridial surface is in the upper part of the sporangium covered with dark plasmodic granulations, which are almost completely absent in the vicinity of columella, where it resembles a transparent brownish membrane, containing not numerous vein-like streaks of excreted substance.

In as yet unopened sporangia the regions of subsequent dehiscence are determined in advance, as prominent ridges, covering the sutures along which the peridial wall later cracks, and the free segments and persistent lobes are differentiated. These slips are a product of the thickened margins of the individual fragments of the peridium, bent out at nearly a right angle to the exterior, and interconnected by rows of short, denticle-shaped processes, attached at more or less regular intervals to the margins, and mutually intercalating with each other. These processes are narrower at their point of origin and broader at their apex, and possess serrated or lacerated extremities. On the opening of the sporangium the processes of each margin detach themselves from the opposite peridial lobe, and the sections thus liberated diverge, whilst their thickened margins become bent out to the exterior. The same conditions apply also to the free scutiform peridial fragments of the upper part of the sporangium.

It will be seen from the above that the mechanism of the opening of the sporangia of *Barbeyella* is considerably more complicated than could be deduced from the descriptions of Meylan¹⁾ and of G. Lister²⁾

Collodermatidae.

Colloderma G. Lister.

39. *Colloderma oculatum* (Lippert). Frequent and widely distributed in the coniferous woods of Czarnohora, at an altitude of 1000 to 1400 m. It is especially abundant during the autumnal months in shaded, damp situations on fallen logs of *Picea*

¹⁾ Ch. Meylan. Myxomycètes du Jura. Bull. de la Soc. Botanique de Genève; sér 2, vol. VI, 1914; pag. 89-90.

²⁾ Miss G. Lister, in discussing the structure of the peridial lobes and plates, merely states that their margins are "slightly reflexed, thickened, and minutely papillose": A Monograph of the Mycetozoa, third ed. 1925, pag. 163.

excelsa, covered with wet moss-tufts and liverworts or covered with a felt of algae. This species is not hitherto recorded from Poland and from the Carpathians.

The plasmodium of this species is, according to my observations, milk-white, and not «purplish-brown», as described by G. Lister, and the earliest phases of the sporangia are also white. With their further development their colour becomes dirty-white, then pale yellow, and finally, grey, brown, and almost black. The external gelatinous peridial envelope of the sporangia possesses the property of imbibing water to a very great extent, as a result of which it swells considerably. Young sporangia are usually associated in larger or smaller groups, enclosed in a common gelatinous mass, in which the dark-coloured sporangia are visible; in this stage they resemble very closely compact masses of frog's eggs. The solitary developing sporangia of *Colloderma*, possess, as is well known, an oculate appearance. The above-mentioned hyaline jelly often contains numerous living algae of the *Protococcales* group.

The external surface of developed, dry sporangia may, contrary to the opinion of G. Lister¹⁾, be occasionally encrusted with minute deposits of CaCO_3 , as has been described by Lippert²⁾.

Physaridae.

Diachea Fries.

40. *Diachea cerifera* G. Lister. Not common. Occurs in late summer and autumn on prostrate logs of *Picea excelsa*, covered with mosses or liverworts, and with overgrowths of algae. Collected at Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz, Mt. Homul, and Mt. Koźmieska, at an altitude of 1250 to 1350 m. August-October 1924 and 1925.

The plasmodium is dirty-white or grayish-white, and the very young, still undifferentiated sporangia are of the same colour.

I was not able to find in the wooded region of Czarnohora any specimen of *Diachea leucopoda* Rostaf., which is so common in lowland situations and occurs also in the lower mountain fo-

¹⁾ A Monograph of Mycetozoa, 3 edit. pag. 129.

²⁾ Ch. Lippert. Über zwei neue Myxomyceten. Verhandlungen der k. k. zoologisch-botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien. XLIV Bd. 1895, pag. 72.

rest belt of the Carpathians in Poland, as well as in Roumania. Meylan was similarly unable to find this species in the high mountain districts of the Swiss Jura¹⁾.

Badhamia Berkeley.

41. *Badhamia panicea* (Fries), Collected once at Mt. Mała Mariszewska on a rotten stump of *Fagus sylvatica*. 14-VIII. 1924.

Physarum Persoon.

42. *Physarum globuliferum* (Bull.). This rather rare species was found once only but in considerable abundance on a mossy stump of *Picea excelsa* at Mt. Pożyżewska. VIII—1925.

43. *Ph. citrinum* Schum. Two large colonies of this were collected on rotten stumps of *Picea excelsa* at Mt. Pożyżewska (15-VII—1924) and at Mt. Dancerz VII—1925.

44. *Ph. viride* (Bull.). Found on several occasions but in scanty colonies on decaying spruce logs. VII—VIII. Mt. Homul. Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Koźmieska.

45. *Ph. nutans* Pers. Found twice during two seasons of my investigations. The very scarce specimens were collected at Mt. Pożyżewska (1924) and at Zaroślak (1925) on rotten spruce wood.

Fuligo Haller.

46. *Fuligo septica* Gmel. Collected at different places of Czarnohora, principally in drier situations. Occurs chiefly on coniferous stumps and fallen spruce-needles.

47. *F. rufa* Pers. Found on old beech-stumps at Wielka Mariszewska and Bystrzec.

The writer, after several years of observations, agrees with the opinions of G. Alexandrowicz, T. H. Macbride and Ch. Meylan²⁾, as well as with the recently published investi-

¹⁾ Ch. Meylan. Recherches sur les Myxomycètes du Jura en 1921—22—23. Bull. de la Soc. Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles. Vol. 55, 1926: pag. 238.

²⁾ Ch. Meylan. Recherches sur les Myxomycètes du Jura en 1921—22—23. Bull. Soc. Vaudoise Sc. Nat. vol. 55, pag. 240.

gations of F. X. Skupiński¹⁾, that *F. rufa*, previously placed by most students as a variety of *F. septica*, can be regarded as an undoubtedly distinct species. In no instance were intermediate forms found. *F. rufa* occurs almost exclusively on dead wood of deciduous trees.

48. *F. muscorum* Alb. et Schw. Rare. Found once in some abundance on mosses in a swamp-forest at Mt. Dancierz 13 VIII--1924.

Leocarpus Link.

49. *Leocarpus fragilis* Rostaf. A single small cluster of sporangia was found at Bystrzec on a dead beech twig. 29 VIII--1925.

Diderma Persoon.

50. *Diderma montanum* Meylan. This species is represented by a single specimen collected on moss at Mt. Homul in September 1925. This is the first Polish record of this species. Dr. M. Brândza reports its frequent occurrence in the mountainous mixed forests of Moldavia.

51. *D. floriforme* Pers. Occurs rather rarely on spruce logs covered with mosses. New to Poland.

52. *D. radiatum* (L.). Not uncommon in Czarnohora but occurs in small quantities. On rotten *Picea* trunks. IX.

Var. *umbilicatum* Pers. Found several times on mossy logs of spruce. September.

Didymiidae.

Spumaria Persoon.

53. *Spumaria spongiosa* (Leysser)²⁾. Very rare. A single specimen of this species was found in October 1924 by Dr. T. Wilczyński upon stems and leaves of *Aira caespitosa* at Mt. Pożyżewska.

¹⁾ F. X. Skupiński. Contribution à l'étude des Myxomycètes en Pologne. Bull. Soc. Mycol. de France. Tome XLII, 1926: pag. 163-168.

²⁾ This name of genus is adopted in place of *Mucilago*, for the reasons given by Jahn in his "Myxomycetenstudien" II., Beobachtungen über seltene Arten. Berichte der Deutschen Botan. Ges. vol. XLI, 1924.

Meylan has also drawn attention to the comparatively rare occurrence of this species in high mountain districts¹⁾.

Lepidoderma de Bary.

54. *Lepidoderma tigrinum* (Schrad.). Frequent in damp and shaded parts of the forests on prostrate logs of *Picea excelsa* covered with wet mosses, lichens and algae. September.

Margaritidae.

Dianema Rex.

55. *Dianema corticatum* Lister. Rare but collected from several localities of Czarnohora. It occurs on decorticated stumps of *Picea excelsa* often in conjunction with *Licea flexuosa* Pers. Bystrzec 28--VIII--1925, Pożyżewska IX--1925, Mt. Dancerz IX--1926.

This species was not hitherto reported from Poland. It was reported recently also from the Moldavian Carpathians by Dr. M. Brândza.

Margarita Lister.

56. *Margarita metallica* (Berk. et Br.). Exceedingly rare. A single group of sporangia in the form of iridescent flat plasmodiocarps was discovered at Mt. Homul (1300m) on a fallen *Picea* log. 7--IX--1925.

No Polish record of this species has been previously published. Dr. M. Brândza reports its frequent occurrence in the mountain forests of Moldavia.

Arcyriidae.

Arcyria Wiggers.

57. *Arcyria ferruginea* Sauter. Not common but collected on several occasions at Mt. Pożyżewska and Mt. Dancerz. July.

58. *A. cinerea* (Bull.). Frequent on decaying logs of coniferous and deciduous trees during the summer and autumn.

¹⁾ See: Bull. Soc. Vaudoise Sc. Naturelles, vol. 55, pag. 238.

59. *A. pomiformis* Rostafiński. Found twice on decorticated trunks of *Picea excelsa*. Mt. Dancerz (VIII—1924) and Mt. Wielka Mariszewska (VIII—1925).

60. *A. denudata* (L.). Not common during the time of my searchings. Collections were made from Mt. Pożyżewska, Mt. Dancerz and Mt. Mała Mariszewska. August.

61. *A. incarnata* (Pers.). Collected several times on dead spruce wood. On one occasion it was found at Mt. Breskul on living *Abies viridis* bark.

62. *A. nutans* (Bull.). This species is very common in all mountain woods of Czarnohora on decaying spruce logs.

Trichiidae.

Trichia Haller.

63. *Trichia faroginea* Pers. This species was collected several times on rotten beech-wood at Bystrzec, Foreszczenka, Mt. Kukul and Mt. Wielka Mariszewska.

64. *T. persimilis* Karsten. Found twice at Bystrzec on dead wood of *Fagus sylvatica*.

65. *T. varia* (Persoon). Collected several times from many localities of Czarnohora.

66. *T. decipiens* (Pers.). This is the most common and abundant species of *Trichia* in all coniferous Czarnohora forests.

Hemitrichia Rostafiński.

67. *Hemitrichia vesparium* (Batsch). Was found twice only on decayed beech-wood. Wielka Mariszewska X--1924, Bystrzec 29—VIII. 1925.

68. *H. karsteni* (Lister). A small group of globose sporangia found at Mt. Pożyżewska on a mossy spruce stump.

69. *H. serputa* (Scop.). In the cracks of a *Fagus sylvatica* stump at Bystrzec (27—VIII—1925) and on rotting logs of *Picea excelsa* at Mt. Homul (IX—1925).

Whilst the greater or lesser frequency of occurrence of a given species is given in the systematic list, I would desire to emphasise the very relative value of data of this type. The data

are often entirely correct for a given season or year, but should not be taken too generally. Mycetozoa are so closely dependent on the most varied ecological factors that some change in their conditions of existence, quite imperceptible to the observer, may exert a fundamental influence on their frequency of occurrence at a given time on the same terrain. For this reason a species which occurred very infrequently in one season may be quite common during the following season, and conversely, Mycetozoa abundantly encountered during one year may be entirely absent during a number of succeeding years.

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